

Pacifying Public Administration As A Discipline To Infuse Africanindigenous Administrative Practices

Mahlala, S, Maramura, T.C, Netswera, F

Article Info	Abstract
<p><i>Article History</i></p> <p>Received: March 14, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: October 15, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Indigenous Public Administration, Public Administration, Afrocentricity, administrativepractices,African.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7200030</p>	<p><i>Public administration, both as an academic discipline and as a field of practice, has not only side-lined but equally rejectedattempts at infusing African administrative practices, deemed as primitive and non-scientific. As a result, Africantraditions, cultures and practices have been unable to provide solutions toAfrican quandaries. One of the main reasons for this dilemma is that public administration is grounded on such theories as the political administrative dichotomy. The tenants of this theoryas reflected in Woodrow Wilson's1887 essay"The Study of Administration" is defined boundaries of public administration and assertion of the normative relationship between elected officials and administrators in a democratic societywhich shaped Public Administration as a discipline and practice throughout the world including Africa.African societies created indigenous administrative systems within their different cultural contexts to manage their own affairsbut these wereside-linedby in favour of the Greek-Roman public administration accumulations. Based on the aforementioned, this paper takes an eccentric approach to smooth out this discourse in view of Afrocentricity. The conceptual nature of the study is supported by a survey of the relevant literature from a range of sources, such as government regulations, media excerpts, and scholarly works.</i></p>

Introduction

This paper contends that if directed by proper African ethical constructions, African administrative systems could promote alternative, successful government systems and address African challenges. However, such remains mythical since African countries have all adopted their colonists' governance theories, frameworks and policies at running their affairs. Moreover, the discipline of Public Administration is repellent of African administrative practices as a foundation for alternative governance. Such is evident as the discipline's foundations are of foreign descent and alien to the daily lived experiences of Africans who in part retains their chiefdoms and cultures. In most public administration writings and curriculum in African institutions as Basheka (2015) has noted and laments, indigenous forms of governance are so severely underappreciated that they seldom receive the considerable scholarly attention they deserve. These historical traditions and practices put immense pressure on modern western trained and inclined public administration scholars and practitioners. Young contemporary scholars and students are caught in struggle between poor appreciation of African indigenous public administration practices and poor comprehension how modern administrative systems whose origin seem murky.

According to (Basheka 2012, Mahlala & Shai, 2022) an important framework for a comparative analysis of African administrative systems should be provided by the requirement to consider how ancient systems were created and maintained over many centuries. Irrespective of the contemporary dispositions, historians should recognize that every civilization historically had its own collective institutions that provided it with a framework for organizing the efforts of men and women to live in harmony and serve the common good. Ramose (1999) thinks that the first requirement for the genuine liberation of Africa is that "the colonized people's notion of reality, knowledge, and truth should be released from enslavement and dominance under the European epistemological paradigm". Moreover, disciplines such as Public Administration in Africa have largely served as a reification of Europe's imperial gaze, which was born of the conquest endeavour. The goal of liberation and decolonization in Africa and other regions of the world that were subject to European imperialism, or any other type of hegemony has often been one of self-determination and the restoration of the people's sovereignty (including sovereignty over self-representation). This argument is further supported by this very paper - that African societies that created indigenous administrative systems within their different cultural contexts to manage their own affairs must not be side-lined but rather should play a major role in revamping the modern state. This paper also argues that African indigenous systems, in particular African administrative system which

were present in Africa before colonization should take centre stage in the study of public administration. This paper begins with a contextual overview of epistemic injustice, ambivalence and decoloniality of African indigenous administrative systems within the discipline, with an emphasis on Africa. This effort is intended to 'deflate and puncture' any arguments advanced by contemporary scholars who believe that pre-colonial African societies lacked any sense of organization and thus could not have had any administrative system worth studying.

Epistemic Injustice of Africa Indigenous public administration

The philosophical study of the nature, origin, and limits of human knowledge is known as epistemology. Furthermore, all humans want to understand the world in which they live, and many of them develop various theories to help them do so. However, because many aspects of the world defy easy explanation, most people are likely to give up at some point and be content with whatever level of understanding they have achieved. It necessitates considering various psychological routes to knowledge, such as logical and scientific reasoning, introspection, perception, memory, testimony, and intuition (Armstrong, 1973 & Turri, 2009). This paper is of the view that, introspection on the repulsion of Public Administration to infuse African indigenous administrative practices in the discipline, to address African issues for which African solutions have not been found.

Moreover, according to Mahlala & Shai (2022), indigenous epistemologies are the cornerstone for building knowledge encompassed around the field of public administration in Africa. Indigenous epistemology also emphasizes the method through which a cultural group creates and validates knowledge, as well as the function of this method in influencing thoughts and behaviour. According to Hart (2010), indigenous epistemology is a flexible mode of knowing that derives from teachings and is passed down through storytelling, where each tale is alive with the subtleties of the storyteller. It is derived from verb-heavy traditional languages, acquired through dreams and visions, and is intuitive and inward-looking. This section of the paper posits that, epistemic injustice of African public administration has been perpetuated without due regard of African administrative systems such as, Ubuntu, the role of elders in society, unity and togetherness which were the lodestar of being an African and how each made systems of African indigenous administration to thrive, which should be used a yardstick to solve modern government quandaries. The section that follows will open a can of worms about Epistemological Warfare in Public Administration. It will also dovetail on how contemporary academics should fearlessly encourage decoloniality of the discipline.

Epistemological Warfare in Public Administration

The purpose of being an academic, or any other type of intellectual, is not only to create and communicate ideas, but also to persuade others of their validity, worth, and implications. But changing people's minds is difficult. It may imply altering how people act and how they believe they should act. Existing beliefs and customs always have staunch supporters, usually for good and bad reasons, and they rarely give up without a fight. Even if they do yield, there are always other competitors vying for readers' loyalty more specifically in the discipline of Public Administration. As a result, all academics worth their salt in decoloniality have become embroiled in controversy at some point during their careers. However, this paper argues that African administrative systems can support effective government systems and aid in the fulfilment of African challenges, which are able to produce African responses, if driven by appropriate African ethical constructs. Scholars such as Ndlove-Gatsheni (2018), in his book *Epistemic Freedom in Africa*, and Basheka (2015), in his paper *Indigenous Africa's Governance Architecture: A Need for African Public Administration Theory*, share this viewpoint. Furthermore, Mahlala and Shai (2022) on their joint paper on *Confronting Challenges and Seizing Opportunities Towards African Indigenous Public Administration* also provide the same arguments.

According to Ndlove-Gatsheni (2018), these decolonial intellectuals share the fundamental beliefs that Africans must think, theorize, interpret the world, and write from where they are without regard for Eurocentrism. However, this has been a difficult endeavour for most scholars, this is because Public Administration is influenced by Woodrow Wilson in his 1887 essay on "The Study of Administration" which shaped the discipline of Public Administration and its practice in Africa. The initial phase represented the realization of Woodrow Wilson's political-administrative dualism (difference between two things as they are completely opposite). This resulted in a surge in interest in its studies at various American and international Universities, and government reforms were implemented, this attracted experts to public administration with renewed energy (Mahlala (2022)). F.W. Taylor and Henri Fayol allegedly intervened and created their management/administration principles, according to (Thornhill, Van Dijk, and Ile, 2015). Because they were successful administrators and well-liked by industries all over the world, their opinions had a lot of merit. Frederick Winslow Taylor and Henri Fayol argued for the adoption of engineering-based scientific methods around industrial work processes in order to increase productivity and economy. Additionally, these schools of thought are included in the classical theory of administration. Max Weber's theoretical approach to bureaucracy, which revolutionized the way public administration is thought about, is particularly noteworthy given that we are discussing the Classical Theorists of Administration (Thornhill (2015)). This paper is of the view that, to this end, much of the literature on the theory and practice of Public Administration has downplayed the contribution of the Africans, their

processes, and institutions in the evolution of the discipline. This epistemic injustice has persisted without regard for the value systems of African societies, each of which developed its own distinct administrative systems within its cultural context, which have left decolonial scholars fighting for cognitive justice and epistemic lines which haunts the twenty-first century. The following section on this paper puts more attention on the decoloniality of Public Administration.

Decoloniality of Public Administration

"Imperialism and colonialism brought complete disorder to colonized people, disconnecting them from their histories, landscapes, languages, social relations, and their own ways of thinking, feeling, and interacting with the world," (Smith, 2012) further writes that decoloniality recognizes that the effects of these forms of cultural imperialism must be undone for those liberated or descended from colonial oppression to thrive. According to Gatsheni (2015) decoloniality is not only a long-standing political and epistemological movement aimed at the liberation of (ex-) colonized peoples from global coloniality but also a way of thinking, knowing, and doing. Decoloniality entails "ongoing colonial undoing" and "understanding of decolonizing methodologies in relation to research, knowledge production, and social criticism" (Hundle, 2019). Nzewi and Maramura (2021: 204) also confirm that, the aim of decoloniality is to encourage institutions of higher learning to apply a decolonizing approach that appreciates the pedagogical value of indigenous knowledge relating to Public Administration as a locus and as a focus. This simply implies that, attempts at decolonization seek to undo the imbalances of the past on African indigenous public administration practices, this view is shared by this paper that the repulsion of Public Administration to infuse African indigenous administrative practices in the discipline has left the fabric of African states reliant on European systems of administration which do not assist in solving African problems.

Such maleficence on the repulsion of Public Administration to infuse African systems of administering and administration has left the state in shambles, this is due to public servants of African states being instructed Eurocentric curricular to administer the public service without due regard of African knowledge systems. According to Bartholomew (1972), the development of public administration as a subject has gone through five stages, each of which is theoretically motivated and is summarized below:

Stage 1: politics administration dichotomy (1887-1926)

Stage 2: principles of administration (1927-1937)

Stage 3: era of challenge (1938-1947)

Stage 4: crises of identity (1948-1970)

Stage 5: public policy perspective (1971 onwards)

Widespread discontentment with the government, its different programs, rife corruption, and the spoils system that predominated in the bureaucratic structure, Woodrow Wilson's viewpoint became visible in the first stage. The second stage is administrative theory, it was assumed that there are some administrative principles (fundamental ideas) that apply to all companies and will maximize efficiency for all (Davies, 1974). The viewpoint of this paper is that, while all these times of development in the discipline are seen to have contributed enormously, this paper denotes such value because these developments did not take place on an African landscape and do not share sentiments on how African problems require African solutions. Moreover, this sentiment is shared by Basheka (2015) on his paper titled: *Indigenous Africa's Governance Architecture: A Need for African Public Administration Theory*. Basheka (2015) posits that, indigenous governance systems are so undervalued that they rarely receive the scholarly attention they deserve in most public administration textbooks and curricula in African universities. This paper is of the view that knowledge of African societies that created indigenous administrative systems within their different cultural contexts to manage their own affairs was side-lined. The paper suggests and shares sentiments with Basheka (2015) that African scholars are primarily obligated to present a more accurate picture of administrative structures and a better understanding of indigenous governance, administration, and management systems, practices that, if well documented, should inform an African public administration theory while also reprimanding epistemic ambivalence from African scholars. This essay's theory of Afrocentricity is supported in the part that follows.

Afrocentricity as an underpinning theory

According to the theoretical underpinnings of Afrocentricity, our primary issue as Africans is our frequently unintentional absorption of the Western worldview, viewpoint, and associated conceptual frameworks (Mazama, 2001). This paper suggests that introspection on the repulsion of Public Administration to infuse African indigenous administrative practices in the discipline, to address African issues for which African solutions have been unable to be found. Moreover, Asante (1991) posits that Afrocentricity, as an intellectual theory, is the study of ideas and events from the perspective of Africans as key players rather than victims. Asante further asserts that this theory becomes a fundamentally empirical project because it has an authentic relationship to the centrality of our own reality. Afrocentricity in essence is Africa's response to asserting itself intellectually and psychologically, breaking the mental chains of Western dominance as an analogy for breaking those chains in every other field even the field of Public Administration. Considering this background, this essay chooses

Afrocentricity as its theoretical and historical framework. This study mainly references the writings of Asante (2003), Mazama (2003), Mafeje (2011), Shai (2020), and other Afrocentric scholars due to the variety of Afrocentric alternatives. This paper suggests for introspection on the repulsion of Public Administration to infuse African indigenous administrative practices in the discipline. Afrocentricity emphasizes the value of developing a triumph consciousness as opposed to spending too much time thinking about oppression. The crucial concept here is "epistemological centeredness" (Mazama, 2003) which on this paper advocates for non-repulsion in Public Administration to infuse African administrative principles.

Epistemic Ambivalence

When you know the truth of a situation but cannot say what the actual underpinnings of such truth are, this is referred to as epistemic ambivalence, because there are multiple options for the truth of what underpins administrative epistemologies (Latour, 1993; Dwyer, 1996; McConaghy, 2000). Simultaneously, understanding the grey areas between "attraction and repulsion" when infusing indigenous administrative practices in Public Administration becomes a critical factor in the scholarly space, where attitudes about what defines Afrocentricity are frequently contradictory. The debate over what constitutes "indigenous administrative practices," and whose interests are served by the infusion and citation of such practices remains a source of concern in the academy. Thus, post-modern and post-colonial literature continues to attempt to address the problems and consequences of driving an Afrocentric curriculum, particularly the consequences of African-centered epistemologies failing to provide African solutions to African quandaries (Shai, 2019). These efforts have seen a surge of interest in recent decades in the dynamics underlying indigenous knowledge practices in Africa, which have been linked to changes in curricula and socio-political orientations, as affirmed in Rio 1992 in increasing the voice and power of indigenous communities and non-Western approaches to knowledge (Agrawal, 1995; Eyzaguirre, 2001).

Thus, in closing the research gap caused by this ambivalence of epistemologies, this paper provides and reveals a significant disengagement between indigenous knowledge systems' perceptions and the realities of African scholars fully engaged in the promotion of these indigenous practices into collaborative processes. According to Kovach (2009) and Shai (2017), the entire discourse of indigenous knowledge practices has been a contentious one. As a result, we cannot continue to ignore how the incorporation of indigenous practices into any curriculum, particularly the discipline of Public Administration, is beneficial from both epistemological and pedagogical standpoints. This paper is also important for improving the scholastic foundation in the Social Sciences and Management Sciences by providing a deeper understanding of the discipline from a consciously African perspective.

According to Mafeje (2008), the challenge for Public Administration as a locus and a focus is the lack of a universal and specifically stated epistemology of indigenous administrative practices. However, Oelofsen observes that the translation of a curriculum whose core is deeply ingrained in what can be called an African philosophical world view goes beyond the never-ending debates over Africa's superiority and inferiority to its former colonial powers (Oelofsen 2015). Furthermore, in this study, we investigate the role of epistemology in providing a new perspective on the ambivalence surrounding indigenous knowledge in Public Administration.

Conclusion

So far, the discussion in this paper has to some extent demonstrated that indigenous knowledge practices mean different things to different people in different places. As much as African historical and cultural administration systems are indigenous to African people, so is Greek-Roman administration to Europeans. What this indicates therefore is that there is a disagreement on some of the characteristics of indigeneity. The paper makes a reasonable attempt at providing a visual representation of not only infusing but putting African Public Administration at the centre from an Afro-centric perspective. As a result, when we talk about indigenous knowledge practices, we should understand connectedness between the academic and the practical domains, creating an appreciation for these complex dynamics. At first glance, this paper appeared to be primarily concerned with how African administrative systems can promote successful government systems and assist in the fulfilment of African challenges by delivering African solutions. In contrast to Western scientific conceptions, African societies have created indigenous administrative systems within their various cultural contexts to manage their own affairs. This paper also demonstrates that when considering the underlying theoretical basis for the conceptualization of Public Administration, the dynamics associated with dissecting indigenous knowledge practices become more complex.

References

- Agrawal, A. 1995. Indigenous and scientific knowledge: some critical comments. *Indigenous Knowledge and Development Monitor* 3 (3): 3-6.
- Armstrong, D.M. 1973, *Belief, Truth and Knowledge*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511570827
- Asante, M.K. 1990. *Kemet, Afrocentricity and knowledge*. Trenton, NJ: Africa World Press.

- Asante, M.K.1991. The Afrocentric idea in education. *Journal of Negro Education*, 60,
- Asante, M.K.2007. *An Afrocentric Manifesto: Toward an African Renaissance*. Malden, MA: Polity Press, 2007.
- Basheka, B.C. 2012. The paradigms of public administration re-examined: A reflection. *Journal of Public Administration*, 47(1), pp.25-67.
- Basheka, B.C. 2015. Indigenous Africa's governance architecture: a need for African public administration theory. *Journal of Public Administration*, 50(3), pp.466-484.
- Davies, W. J. Jr. 1974. "Introduction to Public Administration" in R.J. Stillman (ed.), *Public Administration: Concepts and Cases*. Houghton: Miffling Company.
- Dwyer, M. 1996. Communication and transfer between different knowledge systems. A sequel to the debate (6). *Indigenous Knowledge and Development Monitor* 4(2).
- Eyzaguirre, P. 2001. Global recognition of Indigenous knowledge: is this the latest phase of globalisation? *Indigenous Knowledge and Development Monitor*, 8 (1), pp.1-2. <http://www.nuffic.nl/ciran/ikdm/9-2/column.html>.
- Hundle, A. K. 2019. "Decolonizing Diversity: The Transnational Politics of Minority Racial Difference." *Public Culture*, 31 (2) May 2019, pp. 289-322.
- Kovach, M. 2009. *Indigenous methodologies. Characteristics, conversations, and contexts*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- Latour, B. 1993. *We have never been modern*. Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.
- Latulippe, N. 2015. Bridging Parallel Rows: Epistemic Difference and Relational Accountability in Cross-Cultural Research. *The International Indigenous Policy Journal*, 6(2), pp.1-19. DOI: 10.18584/iipj.2015.6.2.7
- Mafeje, A. 1992. *In Search of an Alternative*. Harare: SAPES.
- Mafeje, A. 2008. "Africanity: A combative ontology." *Bulletin du CODESRIA* 3&4: 106–110.
- Mahlala, S. and Shai, K.B., 2022. Confronting Challenges and Seizing Opportunities Towards African Indigenous Public Administration. *Journal of Public Administration*, 57(1), pp.122-128.
- Mazama, A. 2003. *The Afrocentric Paradigm*. Trenton, New Jersey: Africa World Press, Inc., 2003.
- McConaghy, C. 2000. *Rethinking indigenous education*. Flaxton: Post Pressed.
- Ndlovu-Gatshehi, S.2015. Decoloniality as the Future of Africa. *History Compass*. 13, pp. 485-496. 10.1111/hic3.12264.
- Nzewi, O.I.E. and Maramura, T.C. 2021. A Big Picture Perspective of The Decolonization Of Public Administration Debate In Africa: Looking Back And Looking Forward. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 35 (5), pp.204–215. <https://dx.doi.org/10.20853/35-5-4123>
- Oelofsen, R. 2015. "Decolonisation of the African Mind and Intellectual Landscape". *African Lineage* 16(2), pp. 130–146.
- Shai, K.B. 2017. *South African State Capture: A Symbiotic Affair between Business and State Going Bad (?)*. *Insight on Africa*, 9 (1), pp. 1-14.
- Shai, K.B. 2019. An Afrocentric Narrative of the Chieftaincy Disputes in South Africa with Special Reference to Mamejja and Malepe Traditional Councils. *Journal of Public Administration*, 51 (01), pp. 63-74.
- Smith, T., *Decolonizing Methodologies: Research and Indigenous Peoples*. Zed Books, 2012.
- Turri, J. 2009. "The Ontology of Epistemic Reasons", *Noûs*, 43(3), pp.490–512. doi:10.1111/j.1468-0068.2009.00715.x

Author Information

Mahlala, S

Senior lecturer of Public Management at North-West University

Maramura, T.C

Senior Lecture of Public Management at the Orange Free State University.

Netswera, F

Social Science Research Professor at the Durban University of Technology
